

**Sublime ecologies and artistic endeavours:
artificial life, interactivity and the internet
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Abstract

Art works generated and delivered using digital technology, particularly interactive pieces, challenge established notions of the identity of the artist, the curator and the gallery audience. By chronicling TechnoSphere, an interactive artwork accessed via the internet, I will address some of these issues. It is the development of a grammar of digital media that many practitioners, curators and theorists are engaged with now and some are focussing on the material characteristics of the medium.

TechnoSphere is this type of Modernist project, but it also approaches the medium of the Internet from a more complex matrix of discourses in which issues around representations of landscape and artificial life remain important circuits.

TechnoSphere is an interactive computer-based 'virtual world', a digital ecology whose landscape and artificial life-forms evolve over time. The evolutionary development of the three dimensional world, which is housed on our server, depends on the participation of an on-line public who access the world via the Internet. Users design their own artificial life-forms which are then put into the 3D world. In this fractal terrain trees self-seed at certain heights to make forests [Fig. 1] and there are desert and mountainous regions in which the cyber beasts artificially 'live'. On September 1st 1995 we opened a prototype version which runs over the Internet and is accessed via the World Wide Web¹.

Interaction, virtual galleries and virtual audiences

Gallery sites and artists projects are a relatively new presence on the internet. These Web sites frequently challenge established Netiquette, and simultaneously the traits of the Net throw down a challenge to image-makers, making us rethink our approach to production, exhibition and the audience. Technological innovation, especially the assembly line and mass production has been seen as a way of extending the domain of art, separating it off from its tradition of 'ritual' and 'cult' value. We can view the Internet as another means of extending this domain. Arguments against this type of expansion have been most commonly couched in terms of 'authenticity' and 'aura', extrapolating that the more copies of an artwork that exist, the less the 'aura' and value of the piece. In a Western culture where obvious copies are valued more than the originals by some (for example the cult value of items carrying the Pop Will Eat Itself logo PWEI which was designed in the graphic style of the PEPSI logo) the authenticity debate seems wildly outdated. But if, for the sake of argument, we accept that mechanical and digital reproduction cannot reproduce authenticity, then it can emancipate the work of art from its dependence on ritual.

Many critics have argued that objects lose ritualistic symbolism through mass reproduction, and on the surface this proposition seems reasonable. However, the ritualistic value of, for example, mass produced rosary beads is if anything enhanced rather than reduced by their multiplication, given the social context in which they operate. They may not hold the particular value attributed to a religious relic but they nevertheless retain their symbolic power en masse. The same might be said of computer graphic icons like the Utah Teapot and Mandelbrot's Julia sets, which are frequently used in popular culture to signify a shared belief system. The symbolic power of such images can be applied to artefacts existing in multiple forms in cyberspace: the social context in which they operate (ie the Internet) results in them gaining rather than losing value through being reproduced and existing in multiple states. But the proliferation of virtual art gallery sites on the World Wide Web is happening in a climate where the fetishisation of art objects through ownership is not necessarily dispelled by the production of many digitally reproduced, non-unique versions. The computer as a tool denies the need for traditional specialised techniques and supports plagiarism, multiplicity of sources, technique and reproduction, and the Internet offers a vast library of this type of material.

Computer networks and satellite TV could offer an accessible means of exhibition/ownership to counter the gallery system, allowing anyone with a modem to import images into their homes/work places and record them. As telephone networks become faster the cost of importing images across modems will become cheaper increasing accessibility further. The traditional art distribution system (the gallery) initially responded to this new means of production and distribution by attempting to devalue the art made with computers. As the production continued and expanded the response by the established art world has been to try and contain it. However, curating cyberspace presents a number of challenges to the art establishment, even those bodies historically associated with the radical side of curation. The Net is particularly problematic as a distribution network for art because there is no videotape or CDROM to take away as hard 'fixed' evidence of the work.

After years of striving for full motion and high resolution computer graphical images, using the net as a medium challenges artists used to photographic and film processes to think of new approaches to making their work. Most users can access information over their phone lines via their modems at 2k/second, therefore big image files take a long time to download and users log off the website out of boredom and impatience as they visualise the rise of their telephone bills. The page from Creature Designer [Fig. 2] that is used to design artificial life-forms uses images that have been treated in PhotoShop to reduce the colour palettes to a minimum. Each component uses about 890bytes. Colour stripping images is laborious but makes images load much faster. There are sites on the net which house large high resolution images, but many take the approach of artAIDS LINK² and provide small lower resolution versions, you only load the larger ones if you are especially

interested in them. The quality of image resolution was not what drew me to consider the internet as a site for my artwork. In its most common form the internet and the browsers designed for accessing it provide us with a means of *browsing* text-based information. TechnoSphere is more than an information environment for browsing, it enables users to transgress the clearly delineated division between artist and spectator. It treats the internet as an interface by building a project which is primarily about interaction: using the Internet is as a delivery system for art, which seems particularly appropriate for TechnoSphere which focusses on process and interaction.

The nature of these interactions is varied. There is the interaction of the user with the design pages that they use to create artificial life forms, the interaction between them and their creature as they receive email information about it, and there is interaction between users and the design team as we makes changes to the website and work on additional functions in response to the comments and suggestions that we get from users [Fig. 3]. With people making suggestions for developing the behavioural characteristics of the artificial life-forms the development of functions like the rule system become evolutionary and collective. In effect the development of TechnoSphere is a global collaboration depending on a vast network of users spread around the world, and effected by their ideas and requests. Ultimately the dynamism and look of TechnoSphere itself, its 3D terrain and artificial life, depends on the creatures interacting, and these are based on the artificial life programme that drives these interactions. The theme of interaction is played out from the bottom (the source code of the artificial life software) to the top (the end users).

The net offers the artist opportunities to engage in a dialogue with the audience on a scale which is unusual 'In Real Life' galleries and exhibition spaces. Ultimately this dialogue can become a collaboration and result in the blurring of boundaries between the artist and the audience. Internet users have almost grown to expect the option of commenting via email on material that they find on Web sites, so feedback is more readily given than in a gallery situation. These dialogic art practices call into question notions of the single artistic genius as a *modus operandi* for artistic practice. The 'creative genius' definition of the artist has long been questioned³ but projects like TechnoSphere are a test of how far we have accepted a collaborative approach to art production. As visitors to the Website influence the development of the project through their suggestions as well as a result of the actions of the artificial 'creatures' that they design, they become collaborators. Using email as the medium for dialogue challenges definitions of collaboration further as email correspondents are impossible to authenticate and can send in suggestions anonymously.

Interactive art has become a buzzword, a catchall phrase which is used to describe a huge range of different types of project. The artist Tessa Elliott⁴ makes a clear distinction between what she calls interactive and reactive art works. What Elliott would call reactive are projects which respond to your interaction in a limited and pre-

defined way. Your interaction triggers images and sounds which are finite and determined by the artist. For a piece to be fully interactive in Elliott's terms it's content has to be able to be changed or developed by the interactions of the audience. It is the potential for this type of fuller interaction that drew us to work on the internet, and this is what we are trying to achieve with TechnoSphere.

The interaction between cyber-beasts within TechnoSphere and the designers outside are not just activated by the human designers. At key moments in its evolution, an artificial life-form will email a postcard to its maker to inform them of important changes in its digital evolution [Fig. 4]. This is a bit like the Christmas cards that people receive on behalf of donkeys they have sponsored in sanctuaries, but in the case of the artificial life-forms the postcard is prompted by a significant development, things like extinction, rapid proliferation or dramatic change in appearance as a result of cross-breeding or algorithm-splicing. Users will soon be able to follow the progress of their own creatures, or that of a pre-existing creature by clicking a button on the Web pages to request information. They will get a report of the creature's life and a 2D image of its latest appearance and location. Animations and snapshots of areas and events in the world will also be produced at regular intervals and can be sent over the Internet to interested users.

One future development in TechnoSphere will be the production of a Multi User Domain, to fulfil the needs of users who want to discuss issues raised by TechnoSphere and meet the designers of other creatures and talk about artificial life, social behaviour and evolution in virtual worlds. Traditional rites of passage rituals draw attention to the role of the social in many of the biological, cultural and technological changes that humankind has experienced. Rites of passage⁵ articulate human identities and bodies from one social position to another, for example puberty rites of passage articulate the biological and cultural passage from child to adult. Cyberspace can be seen as a mediation between human and post-human, between analogue and digital centred around the social and symbolic transformation of the body. A cyber-spatial rite of passage might be the assumption of a digital identity on the Net. Not only is this a rite of passage from organic to transorganic, from analogue to digital, but often it involves a key change in identity such as computer cross-dressing. It is apparent from some of the email that I receive that the designers of TechnoSphere's artificial creatures often identify with them to the extent that they see them as digital agents, as representing themselves whether this is as a carnivore with a chainsaw head or as one of a herd of herbivores. The process of designing an artificial life form includes for many users an interpretation of the project which assumes that they delegate their agency to representations of themselves (digital creatures) that exist in virtual space alongside representations of other people. The processes of design and the subsequent text-based and visual feedback that they get from their creatures becomes a kind of rite of passage for users. This takes them from the real world where they may be sitting in front of their computer screens eating pot-noodle to the heady virtual possibilities of cyberspace, where no-one

needs to know their age, colour, sex or ability but perceives them via their artificial life form. An extreme view would hold that to access our web site is to symbolically enter a different social space.

Interactive art has changed both artists and curators understanding of 'the audience'. Works which are exhibited on the Internet initiate a further rethinking. The notion of audience monitoring is especially important in Arts Council of England (ACE) funded projects and Internet based works provide a new challenge to the way galleries and funding bodies take audiences into account. The potential audience for these projects is huge in comparison to the numbers of people likely to visit any particular gallery exhibition, but on the other hand they are unlikely to be limited to a country let alone a specific geographical region. Traditional ACE notions of conveniently targeting local audiences are thrown wide open, and specific local audiences might need to be drawn in through workshops and tours. While problematising 'the audience', Net-based works have a readily available methods for evaluating and identifying the audience. For example a simple option to sign a visitors book (and leave an email address which is common practice on entering Internet sites) will provide a record of the people accessing and interacting with the project.

Rather than engaging with the particular qualities that distinguish the Internet from other artistic media, numerous virtual art gallery sites on the Web have all the trappings of the art market, epitomised by an obsession with ownership and control. This is illustrated by a common sight that greets you when you access many on-line gallery sites - the first thing that you read is a warning against reproducing the images on display, which are shown at deliberately low-resolution to put users off copying them. By contrast TechnoSphere could be seen as a Modernist project, attempting to engage with the specificity of the Internet and characterised by the traits of the net, many of which seem in opposition to ideas of control of information. Like any computer programme TechnoSphere can be copied and run on many machines at the same time. As this happens there will be many Technospheres existing simultaneously, all looking different from each other as their look depends on the artificial life-forms that inhabit them. However, the difference is no longer of the nature historically associated with works of art, it is unrelated to notions of 'stages of development' or 'level of completion'. All versions are authentic, or none are authentic, in fact authenticity becomes irrelevant. Engaging with levels of interaction, and the characteristics of the Internet is are key themes in Technosphere. But our attempts to develop a grammar of digital media is equally important. This interest is reflected in our explorations of the paradox of computer simulations of nature, nature as symbolised by images of landscapes and via the use of artificial life.

Artificial nature and the sublime

In the late seventeenth century there emerged a new and sweeping feeling for nature and natural beauty. Alongside art, nature became a subject worthy of aesthetic contemplation. With its vast scale, sweeping landscapes and impenetrable mountain

ranges, nature partook of, and indeed largely sustained the aesthetic of the sublime. An overwhelming sense of overpowering scale felt by those contemplating nature was thought to prompt consideration of the Infinite God who had created it, allowing religious experience to share blurred boundaries with the aesthetic sublime. In contemporary Western societies, ideas of nature as sublime have eroded somewhat as we have been able to “conquer” even the highest peaks, and have lost most of our opportunities to view vast expanses of landscapes through the expansion of building and an increase in air pollution which renders the horizon less visible. Paradoxically computer simulations of nature highlight our current dilemma allowing us to experience a nostalgia and yearning for a sublime, unconquerable nature. Simultaneously we revel in our ability to reconstitute an “improved” awesome wilderness through digital technologies.

In the fractal landscapes of TechnoSphere’s terrain we are not striving for a digital Eden which replicates the natural world in an ordered form. Nor are we striving to perfect nature via geometry to accelerate the natural sublime. Mathematics has offered frameworks through which to redefine artistic practice by using mathematic harmonic structures to reveal previously hidden cosmic structure (Euclidean and Pythagorean mathematics in particular tried this.) By contrast we are using fractal mathematics, not just to create a complex-looking terrain, but as an embodiment of anti-reductionist approach to the production of images. Unlike Pythagorean and Euclidean geometry fractal mathematics does not offer a simple equation for creating natural variation, instead it describes dynamic systems themselves. In the nineteen nineties chaos theory is having an impact on aesthetics and taste similar in magnitude to the impact of the sublime in the seventeenth century. Chaos theory provides a rationale for those events previously inexplicable and random which were traditionally given form through art and poetry. The association of irregularity and a degree of disorder with creativity and art images continues to the present day, and has been central to critical debates surrounding computer images since the observations of Meyer Shapiro following the Cybernetic Serendipity⁶ exhibition in 1968. This focused on a series of pictures produced by A. Michael Noll which used semi randomness to create images strikingly similar to Piet Mondrian’s Composition With Lines 1917. Viewers found it impossible to differentiate Mondrian’s image from that generated by the computer (only 28% could identify which was which) in addition 59% preferred Noll’s plotter pictures⁶. Looking at them it may well be do with our strong cultural association of randomness with creativity, resulting in an assumption that the most random looking images must be the painter’s [Fig. 5].

There are those who interpret computer simulations such as TechnoSphere as an attempt at taming sublime nature to new notions of proper mathematical order, or to take this a stage further who see TechnoSphere as a Utopia where we, the designers, play God. There are some important differences to be drawn between the design and implementation of artificial life-forms and any attempt to play at being a deity. Firstly, if we accept this analogy, there is no single 'God' in the production of

TechnoSphere, every user that sends in a design has the ability to 'create' a life-form. Secondly, the life-forms develop via unnatural selection rather than being paired off or destroyed by us. Users cannot interfere with the development of the life-form that they sent in once it is in the virtual world. At the most we provide a mathematical model which has rules, this is not a God-like activity, more social one, such as the making of laws or rules of behaviour. As there are opportunities for users to make suggestions for changes or additions to these rules by emailing, or leaving messages at the Web site, the development of the rule system is evolutionary and collective.

Through the dissemination of fractal images and the greater realisations of the aestheticising implications of chaos theory, there is emerging a renewed interest in detail, and a sense of the "sublime" having its equivalent in cyberspace - the unexplored, unconquered and unknown realms of the digital world of electronic signals, networks and remote human presence. Although traditionally the sublime is connected with the overwhelmingly large, we seem to be experiencing a cultural shift in taste which is parallel to an intellectual response to theories expounded by physicists like Stephen Hawking⁷, who see a kind of sublimity in the microcosmic world of particle systems. It is the very small and the very detailed which now prompt the "great thoughts and passions". We are challenged by the microscopic scale of things, just as vast expanses of nature once challenged philosophers of aesthetics like Shaftesbury⁸. While Shaftesbury's sublime was too big for us to grasp comfortably, Hawking's is perhaps too small.

In TechnoSphere's rendering of the terrains there are traces of the seduction of using the computer to create mimetic images of lost and ideal sublime landscapes (the fractal mountains and mists), but these are fractured and intertwined with the wish to make explicit the landscape's artifice and digital origin as seen in the three levels of rendered land [Fig. 6]. This type of rendering was a response to our wish to find digital alternatives to the use of cinematic devices which are so often used wholesale in computer graphics to attract the viewers attention, devices such as depth of field and focus. Combining three types of rendering in one view is our algorithmic alternative to focus and depth of field.

In many computer images pure information and the relationship between information is frequently represented in a highly plastic form (we don't see the code on screen). To counter this the TechnoSphere programme code will be mapped onto whirlwinds as a texture alluding to the binary and algorithmic nature of the landscape's origins. Another way of emphasising TechnoSphere's artifice can be seen in our choice to make the artificial life forms non-biological in appearance. It has been said that a work of art is as much about relations of tension as it is about attempts to resolve them⁹, with this in mind we are trying to embed traces of these tensions and fractures in the imagery of the virtual world. The rendering is one example of this.

The aesthetic sublime of the seventeenth century included an element of divinity.

Most of our definitions of life continue to have a mystical and supernatural component, despite the increasing use of empirical methods to recognise life¹⁰. Artificial life remains controversial area of research, as we have found when we have given presentations on TechnoSphere in galleries and members of the audience have angrily accused us of playing God. Rather than dismissing these responses it may be more interesting to try and decipher why they are generated. Having explored this it seems that people tend to make an associative leap from artificial life to genetic engineering. Amongst the myriad of reasons why genetic engineering disturbs so many is the powerful cultural belief that designing life is God's business and that artificial life is an example of devilish meddling! even when 'life' is artificial and restricted to a digital domain the association with divinity is perpetuated.

Artificial life in TechnoSphere

Central to artificial life programmes is the assertion that life depends on a certain level of complexity¹⁰. This might seem obvious to us now, as we live in an age where chaos theory has been popularised, but it was a radical proposition when first expounded in the 1950s. This dependency on complexity was one key step away from the reductionist approach to discovering the principles of evolution of biological organisms which was common in the physical sciences. A movement away from reductionist theories and towards ideas of synthesis again fits in with larger cultural shifts in the West which have seen us discard metanarratives as viable interpretations of the world and move towards a postmodernist synthesis or eclecticism. Importantly these complex systems can emerge from a relatively simple set of rules. In TechnoSphere our simple rules have resulted in some surprising moments such as what we have called "vending machine valley". In this example carnivores formed a huge semi-circular group at the mouth of a sealed valley which is an inlet to some mountains. Trapped in the fractal corral, herds of herbivores grazed until the lack of grass drove them inevitably out of the valley and into the virtual jaws of the waiting carnivores (which had not ventured into the corral but merely waited outside). The notion of self-organising artificial life systems which we have used in TechnoSphere depend on a 'bottom-up' approach, with behaviour emerging as artificial creatures interact, rather than us imposing a 'top down' control on behaviour. This idea of 'bottom up' evolution has been applied to the whole project and carried through to the design process. By taking the calculated risk of developing the project on-line, starting with a simple version on the internet, we can engage in bottom up development in conjunction with the thousands of users who access the web site and send us emails about the project.

In conclusion the excitement caused by interactivity and interconnection can be seen as part of a larger cultural development. Interconnectivity has become one of the paradigms of the late Twentieth century as our interpretation of the world has been dramatically affected by scientific discoveries, such as chaos theory which has provided us with a model which recognises the importance and power of interaction. There seems to be a dilemma inspired by TechnoSphere, a concern about its

metaphors of landscape [Fig.7] and our metaphoric use of terms like 'creature' to describe the artificial life-forms, the code that drives it as a database. Also, there is a larger cultural dis-ease with computer simulations of nature which is subtle but persistent. Rather than a dilemma, it seems to us that TechnoSphere could be seen as having a kind of gestalt effect: of being simultaneously metaphoric or allegorical, and mimetic, mimetic in that as you look at it the 3D terrain seems recognisable, there is a pleasure in that recognition although the recognition is not total, the mimesis is interrupted by a flat facet or an improbable life-form and we are reminded of the digital source of the image.

References

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References for illustrations

Fig.1 TechnoSphere: scene from the fractal landscape. Automatically generated and rendered using software written by Gordon Selley.

Fig. 2 TechnoSphere: one of the pages on the World Wide Web which users use to design artificial life forms. Creature components modelled by Andrew Kind.

Fig. 3 TechnoSphere: the Comments page. Between 20 and 200 comments a day get sent to the design team via this interface.

Fig. 4 TechnoSphere: a virtual postcard. Users view postcards on the Web site before downloading them or making links to them from their own Web sites.

Fig. 5 Comparison of Mondrian's Composition with Lines 1917 (on the left) and a computer generated picture by A. Michael Noll of Bell Laboratories⁶

Fig. 6 TechnoSphere: scene from TechnoSphere showing experiments with rendering techniques to find digital alternatives to cinematic devices to attract the viewers gaze.

Fig. 7 TechnoSphere: scene from a fractal forest, with mountainous regions in the background.